

Islam in Hausaland

By Abdul mumin Alawiye, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria

Entry tags: Sufi, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Arabic, Shi'a Islam, Islam, Hausa Language, Sunni Islam, Language, English

Defining the Hausaland is somewhat quagmire. This is because some scholars give its definition based on the land where people's mother tongue is Hausa language. Meanwhile, the land covers in the main a large area of northern Nigeria and part of the present-day Republic of Niger. The territory of the Hausa states lay above the confluence of the Niger and Benue rivers (in present-day northern Nigeria), between the Songhai empire in the west and that of the Kanem-Bornu, or Bornu, in the east. The seven true Hausa states, or Hausa Bakwai (Biram, Daura, Gobir, Kano, Katsina, Rano, and Zaria (Zazzau), and their seven outlying satellites, or Bansa Bakwai (Zamfara, Kebbi, Yauri, Gwari, Nupe, Kororofa (Jukun), and Yoruba), had no central authority, were never combined in wars of conquest, and were therefore frequently subject to domination from outside. The historians had spoken with one voice regarding the origin of the Hausaland. They opined that the original seven kingdoms of the Hausaland were traceable to a Muslim Arab man called Abu Zayd or Hawdhah. The latter left his native land (Baghdad) to this part of Nigeria in the late 8th century. He then rambled the land till he arrived at the place called Daura. Thereafter, his grandchildren later became the seven Hausa rulers of Daura, Kano, Katsina, Zazzaki, Zamfara, Rano and Buram. It is believed that this Muslim Arab man tended to be a survival of the Umayyad people displaced as a result of the Abbasid people that had toppled their dynasty. Thus, this man might have been responsible for the introduction of Islam in the society, and the nature of the idolaters who used to revert to their former faith might have made Islam to later become a thing of the past in the society. As far as the advent of Islam in Hausaland, scores of scholarly historians have written at great length on the topic. According to the Kano Chronicle, a Muslim community had been found in Kano by the middle of the 14th century. The introduction of Islam into the society is said to have been traceable to some missionaries who hailed from Mali. In another historical account on the advent of Islam in Hausaland, Katsina, which is regarded as the seat of civilization and culture, some of its indigenes are said to have been the pioneer Muslims. This is because the city is topographically situated the route of the traversing caravans from Timbuktu to Borno and Egypt. And there was a big market there that the Barbarians, Wangara and the Arabs used to patronize in the middle of the 12th century. The precise date of the advent of Islam in Katsina is unknown; but the inhabitants of this region had been in contact with Islam since time immemorial. Meanwhile, the spread of Islam to Kano in the 13th century is believed to have been precipitated by the influx of the Wangara to place. Muhammad Ibn Abd al-Karim al-Maghili, a Berber Islamic scholar, in the course of touring North and West Africa also arrived in Kano in 1492 while on a journey that took him to Mecca as well as Air, Gao and Katsina among other places. In the course of his stopover at Kano, he organized and saw to the religious needs of the North Africa community there. Besides, it was chronicled that he handwrote a Qur'ān for the people of Kano, for he had not brought a copy with him, and had to teach the Qur'ān and the punishment of the law. The visitation of al-Maghili to Kano took place in the second half of the 15th century during Muhammad Rumfa's regime (1463-1499), and that had enhanced the stability of Islam and the spread of the Islamic guidelines in this part of the world. This writing is concerned about the Hausa people, their belief system, how Islam was brought into being in Hausa-land, and its impact on the lives of the people there. It deals with the ancient cities like Kano, Katsina, Zaria, Daura, Kebbi and so on, which are situated in the present day northern Nigeria.

Date Range: 1500 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Hausaland

Region tags: Northern Nigeria, Add the map for me
using the map of Southeastern Nigeria

The Hausaland of Nigeria from 1500

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: West Africa and Islam by Peter B. Clarke
- Source 1: Al-Islam Fi Nayjiritah wa al-Shaykh Uthman Bin Fudi al-Fulani by Adam Abdullah al-Ilori
- Source 2: The Kano Chronicle by H. R. Palmer Source: The Journal of the Royal Anthropological Institute of Great Britain and Ireland, Vol. 38 (Jan. - Jun., 1908), pp. 58-98
- Source 3: Towards a Less Orthodox History of Hausaland by J. E. G. Sutton Source: The Journal of African History, 1979, Vol. 20, No. 2 (1979), pp. 179-201 Published by: Cambridge University Press

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/220388>
- Source 1 Description: Tubali: Hausa Architecture of Northern Nigeria by Sabine Jell-Bahlsen
- Source 2 URL: <file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/THE%20ARCHITECTURE%20OF%20THE.pdf>
- Source 2 Description: THE ARCHITECTURE OF THE WEST AFRICAN MOSQUE An Exegesis of the Hausa and Fulani Models

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://ar.islamway.net/article/61409/>
- Source 1 Description: islamway.net
- Source 1 URL: <https://sunnah.com/ibnmajah:1636>
- Source 1 Description: Sunnan Ibn Majah
- Source 1 URL: <file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/EJC-d44e03850-1.pdf>
- Source 1 Description: A History of Shia and its Development in Nigeria: The Case-Study of Kano
- Source 1 URL: <file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/EJC-d44e03850.pdf>
- Source 1 Description: Unisa Press Journals
- Source 1 URL: <https://quranyusufali.com/5/>
- Source 1 Description: The Holy Qur'an Translation By A. Yusuf Ali
- Source 1 URL: <https://sunnah.com/bukhari:1338>
- Source 1 Description: Sahih al-Bukhari

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: There is also Islamic movement of Nigeria (Shia) in the Hausa society whose emergence dates back to the early 80's of the last century.

– Yes

Notes: There is also Sufi order like Quadriyyah and Tijaniyyah. The Sufi order had been in existence in the Hausaland before any other group in the society.

– Yes

Notes: There is also Jamā'at Izālat al-Bid'a wa-Iqāmat al-Sunna (Society for the Removal of Innovations and Reinstatement of Sunnah (Tradition)). This Izala movement is aimed to curb all forms of heretical occurrences in the Islamic society.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Assigned by personal choice:

– No

Assigned by class:

– No

Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Assigned by gender:

– No

Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: In Sufi order, the disciples pledge allegiance to the Sheikh serving as their spiritual leader. They pledges to follow him on the path of abandoning faults, displaying good qualities, achieving the pillar of benevolence, and advancing in their stations. In Shiism, the version of the

kalmah Shahada (the Islamic profession of faith) differs from that of the Sunni. The Sunnī version of the Shahada is: "There is no god except God, Muhammad is the messenger of God", but the Shia Muslims append the phrase Aliyun-Waliyullah (Ali is the Waliyullah (custodian of God)).

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Members of Shiism in Kano often attend the activities of Sufi orders in the city, and its leadership always look for an avenue to foster a close relationship with them. The Shiites have things to gain from this relationship, because it gives them recognition and an opportunity to propagate their doctrine. The Shiites have also used this window to attract some followers from Sufi groups. Besides, the Shiites hold gatherings (halaqat) in different places where they disseminate their ideology.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The Shiites are advocating for the transformation of Nigeria into a 'purely Islamic' form of government under the platform named 'Muslim Brothers' which is popularly known in Kano and other parts of northern Nigeria. They are looking for ways to get represented into the Nigerian government with a view to achieving their aspiration.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The majority of the jurists of Sunni and Shia affiliations are of the view that apostasy from Islam is a sinful crime and punishable by the death penalty. However, there are options for leniency (such as giving room for repentance and delaying the execution).

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

– No

Notes: That is, the apostates will be set free with their quick repentance.

– Yes

Notes: If the apostates fail to repent, they are eventually prosecuted.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: The majority of the Nigerian Muslim population is Sunni, there is a small Shia minority, particularly in the northern states of Kano, Kaduna and so on. Many Muslims are still combining Sunni and Sufi practices in the society. Thus, the population of the Sufi adherents is very high too.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Glorious Qur'an is the divine Scripture of all the groups. Only the application of what obtains in this divine Scripture varies in the life of individual group in the society.

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: The high God here stands for the almighty Allah who had given many of His messengers divine Scriptures. Meanwhile the revelation of the Qur'an to the Prophet of Islam endured twenty-three years. It started one day while Muhammad was asleep in the Cave of Hira, where he used to go with a view to meditating and thinking over the wonderful creatures. The arch angel Jibril appeared to him with a sheet in his hand and said to him "Read" Muhammad answered in surprise "What shall I read?" for the second time, the angel again commanded him "Read", and Muhammad again responded with

the plea "What shall I read?" For the third time, Muhammad was seized by the angel and he commanded "Read in the name of your Lord, the creator, who created man from clot of blood. Read! Your Lord is Gracious. He who taught man by the pen that which he knows not". This marked the dawn of Quranic revelation.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Wahy simply implies divine inspiration. It is one of the three modes of revelation according to the Qur'an chapter 42 verse 51 which goes thus: "It is not fitting for a man that God should speak to him except by inspiration, or from behind a veil, or by sending a messenger to reveal with God's permission what God wills for He is Most High, Most Wise".

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: There are Gidan Rumfa in Kano, Kano Museum, an example of Hausa Tubali architecture, Gobarau Minaret in Katsina and so on.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– I don't know

Is iconography present:

– I don't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: There are sacred sites meant as cemeteries for the burial of the dead Muslims; while Muslim praying-grounds for Eidul Fitr (after the completion of Ramadan fast) and Eidul Adha respectively.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: Pilgrimage is one of the five fundamentals of Islam which only takes place at Mecca/Medina. The major activities of the institution of Hajj (pilgrimage) are doing at the Mecca, the Prophet's native land like ,circumambulation around the sacred house of Allah (kaaba), Arafa and so on; while the holy visitation to Medina is also considered as an integral part of the rite of Hajj. The Prophet's mosque and his burial are situated in the city of Medina. Thus, the eligible Muslims, that is those who are healthy and financially capable, all over the world only gravitate towards the two sacred places (Mecca and Medina) with a view to performing their pilgrimage.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: According to the Prophetic tradition, when a dead body has been buried, the angels in charge of the grave will visit such a person and seat him/her for interrogation. All the creatures around will be hearing that except the mankind and Jinn. The detail about the scenario is couched in the Sahih al-Bukhari (Hadith: 1338), the tradition reads: "The Prophet (ﷺ) said, "When a human being is laid in his grave and his companions return and he even hears their foot steps, two angels come to him and make him sit and ask him: What did you use to say about this man, Muhammad ? He will say: I testify that he is Allah's slave and His Apostle. Then it will be said to him, 'Look at your place in the Hell-Fire. Allah has given you a place in Paradise instead of it.' " The Prophet (ﷺ) added, "The dead person will see both his places. But a non-believer or a hypocrite will say to the angels, 'I do not know, but I used to say what the people used to say! It will be said to him, 'Neither did you know nor did you take the guidance (by reciting the Qur'an).' Then he will be hit with an iron hammer between his two ears, and he will cry and that cry will be heard by whatever approaches him except human beings and jinns." Thus, this shows that the dead has only undergone a kind of transition from the surface of earth to the eschatological life.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Only the soul personifies and is being dealt with in this situation; there is no physical movement of the other parts of the body like when the person was alive.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

– Yes

Other spirit-body relationship:

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Muslims irrespective of their organizational and sectarian differences generally believe that there is life after death. This has been abundantly explained in the Quran chapter 22 verse 7 thus: "And [that they may know] that the Hour is coming- no doubt about it- and that Allah will resurrect those in the graves.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: The Islamic law (Shrariah) does not support this belief that tends to lead people to infidelity. Once a person has died that is the end of the life on the surface of earth. The belief of people in reincarnation is a kind of enigma.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: The Prophet is reported to have said: "Allah has forbidden the earth to consume the bodies of the Prophets." Thus, the corpses of the Prophets are considered more sacred than the ordinary people.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: In Islam, the burial of the corpse is not delayed or given unnecessary ostentatious practices that are opposed to the Prophetic injunctions contained in the general Islamic guidelines.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: God does not possess all the characteristic features of humans. This is because His life has neither the beginning nor the end. In Islamic guidelines, attributing the qualities of humans to the almighty Creator, which is known as anthropomorphism, is synonymous with infidelity or associating partners with Him which is considered as the gravest and unforgivable sinful act.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: The supreme high God is unique and not likened to all the created phenomena

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: His knowledge encompasses all the existent beings in the heaven and on the earth.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: His knowledge encompasses all human and non-human affairs.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

–Yes [specify]: He has the knowledge of time, what is in the womb, what one will invest in tomorrow, and so on.

Notes: The testimony of the supreme God's encompassing knowledge goes thus: "Indeed, Allah alone has the knowledge of the Hour. He sends down the rain and knows what is in the wombs. No soul knows what it will earn for tomorrow, and no soul knows in what land it will die. Surely Allah is All-Knowing, All-Aware" (Q.31: 34).

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: In Islamic doctrine, worshipping any other created or supernatural beings other than the the almighty God amounts to shirk- associating partners with Allah, the Supreme Being.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

–Yes [specify]: The supreme god is Eternal, One, Omniscient, Everliving and so on.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Like His communication with His Prophet called Ibrahim (Abraham). This could be sourced from the Quran chapter 37 verse 102 where Allah asked the latter to sacrifice His son.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Inspiration, through Angel.

Notes: In the Quran chapter 42 verse 51, the mediums of communication between God and humans have been unequivocally disclosed thus: "It is not given to any human being that Allah should speak to him unless (it be) by Inspiration, or from behind a veil, or (that) He sends a Messenger to reveal what He wills by His Leave, Surely He is Most High, Most Wise".

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: If God wills.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: Like the angels assigned to be overseeing human affairs.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: As designed by the supreme God.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Notes: The supreme God determines the restriction of non-human supernatural beings. Only the knowledge of the supreme God is unrestricted.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: Like the angels following the supreme God's permission.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

Notes: Only God sees inside heart/mind. It has been said in the glorious Quran thus: " He certainly has the (full) knowledge of, of the secrets of (all) hearts" (Q.67:13).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

Notes: Only the High God (Allah) knows everything. He says: "Allah is He, than Whom there is no other god;- Who knows (all things) both secret and open; He Most Gracious, Most Merciful" (Q.59: 22).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: With the supreme God's knowledge and permission.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: With the supreme God's knowledge and permission.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Notes: The angels, as supernatural beings, do not possess this feature.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They do not have freewill. They abide by the supreme God's instruction without hesitation.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Fornication, lesbianism, homosexuality

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the adherents of Shiism and Sufism tend to be very messianic when they call on their leaders, particularly the departed ones, to be of help to them in sorting out their problems in life. Some do this as a result of their sheer ignorance of Islamic guidelines, or as a result of their ungovernable whims and caprices. This continues to make the Sunni adherents to vehemently crucify them for their heretical practices which are not found in the pristine tenets of the religion. They even go to the extent of accusing them of infidelity, because they consider the malpractices of the Shiites and Sufis to have opposed the implicature of *kalmatu-sh-shahadah* (word of declaration as a Muslim) that they proclaim and say individually and publicly.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Some religious groups adopt the conventional social norms prescribed by the Islamic guidelines,

and try to blend some with a view to satisfying their ulterior motive.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Weakly present

Notes: Laxity and extremism are two features identifiable with some of the religious groups.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The adherents of the religious groups sometimes have some specific ways of addressing their leaders and fellows which are not traceable to Islamic guidelines.

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within contemporary world

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Generally, celibacy is proscribed in Islam. The prophet of Islam was married, and he had enjoined his followers to get married when they attain the marriageable age and become physically and morally okay. The injunction even begins from the Quranic quotation thus: "... then marry other women of your choice- two, three, or four. But if you are afraid you will fail to maintain justice, then content yourselves with one or those bondwomen in your possession..." (Q. 4: 3).

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Fasting may be recommended by some religious group leaders in the name of enhancing spiritual elevation of the members. The days may be in line with the application of Prophetic traditions, if the leaders are very conscious of Sunnah (Prophetic tradition). While some leaders may just recommend the fasting out of their own volition. Meanwhile, the Sunni group only takes cognizance of the prophetic prescriptions in respect of fasting without indulging in heresy.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes, some Sufi order may be recommending that that their members should eschew some foods that involve meat, fish or animals that are considered lawful according to Islamic guidelines. Their belief is that by taking such foods, one tends to forget to remember Allah. They believe that the fish caught in the river was as result of its failure to glorify God. Thus, taking such fish tends to make one forget to engage in dhikr (remembrance of Allah).

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: The members are expected to sacrifice their time to attend the programs organized by the religious groups. This is generally characteristic of all members of the groups, Sufi, Sunni and Shia groups. Through this, the members are being informed of their missions and goals.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: Like the movement of some religious groups while engaging in dhikr which they consider as a spiritual exercise.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: This is characteristic of majority of the religious groups. The Sufi group will be looking down upon the Sunni group; while the Sunni group too will be denigrating the Sufi membership and Shiites.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: They may be slaughtering animals as sacrifice and distribute it the members and the poverty-stricken people in the vicinity.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: They contribute money and materials to be given as alms to the poor and the needy in the name of seeking the pleasure of the Supreme God (Allah).

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Notes: The activities are usually sporadic.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The Sufi group members do count right actions as part of the concept of Ihsan, which is the acme of spiritual elevation.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: This is very common to the adherents of Sufi order and Shiism.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: If some adherents of religious groups who are given to using intoxicants, they do that out of their whimsical tendency. They too know that it is a sinful act.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– I don't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– I don't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– I don't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This may be realized through the good government.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: This is done in order not to lose membership.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: This is done to gain ground in the society and create awareness among the official persons.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: They interact with the institutional bureaucracies that serve as their loyalists and will of help to the progress of their group.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– I don't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– I don't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: This is meant for the facilitation of their programs that require movement to distant places.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes, they can contact the government authority that is their loyalist to request for transportation facility.

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes, they can contact the government authority that is their loyalist to request for transportation facility.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: This is done in form of Sadaqa to enhance the activities of the group.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This depends on the affiliations that the group's adherents may still belong to in the society.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They group's adherents tend to appeal to external judicial system to satisfy their desire.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: In Islamic penal code, a person who intentionally murdered an innocent person should also be executed. The Quran chapter 5 verse 45 reads: "We ordained therein for them: "Life for life eye for eye nose for nose ear for ear tooth for tooth and wounds equal for equal." But if anyone remits the retaliation by way of charity it is an act of atonement for himself. And if any fail to judge by (the light of) what God hath revealed they are (no better than) wrong-doers".

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: There is a reference to some crimes that involve the exile of the culprit as contained in the Quran thus: "The punishment of those who wage war against God and His Apostle and strive with might and main for mischief through the land is: execution or crucifixion of the cutting off of hands and feet from opposite sides or exile from the land: that is their disgrace in this world and a heavy punishment is theirs in the Hereafter" (Q.5: 33)..

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: For instance, the citizens of the country are subject to the government policies. And failure to abide by the rules and regulations laid down by the constituted authority may lead to bringing one to book.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: Like the Shiites, they are having their separate forces to defend the membership against external forces..

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– No

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– No

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: : This is determined by the reaction of the group to the government policy. For instance any religious group tagged as violent and politically influenced tends not to enjoy the government security provision since the group is regarded anti-government.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)